

Performance Prediction for Stommel’s Perpetual Salt Fountain in the Context of Artificial Ocean Upwelling

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Abstract

Due to the typical temperature and salinity structure in wide parts of the global oceans, a self-sustaining, convective up or downflow within a vertical pipe can be established. This concept was introduced by Stommel et al. (1956) as the *perpetual salt fountain*. Recently, Stommel Upwelling Pipe (SUP) systems are gaining new interest as possible enabling technology for large-scale implementations of Artificial Upwelling (AU) of nutrient-rich Deep Ocean Water (DOW) to the ocean surface. This process is currently actively researched as part of several marine Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) approaches. Despite multiple studies conducted over the past decades, no method has yet been proposed to reliably predict performance and thus enable quantification of the potential of Stommel Upwelling Pipe (SUP) systems for AU. In the present work, two performance prediction methods for SUP systems are introduced, one method based on the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations and a one-dimensional method based on pipe flow equations. This twofold approach overcomes the limitations of previous studies and enables reliable performance estimation for a wide range of SUP setups. Both numerical methods are described in the present work, and their predictive capabilities are proven through rigorous verification, validation, and model intercomparison. The respective model assumptions are critically reviewed. Our results reveal key aspects of SUP performance and provide the basis for a reliable evaluation of the potential of SUP systems for AU.

Keywords: Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR), Artificial Upwelling, Perpetual Salt Fountain, Stommel Upwelling Pipe, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), mixed convection

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1. Introduction

In many ocean regions, the surface waters have both higher temperatures and a higher salinity than the Deep Ocean Water (DOW). With regard to density, the temperature effect, which stabilizes the stratification of the water column, outweighs the destabilizing salinity effect. When viewing these ocean regions as a thermodynamic system, it is apparent that the system could be moved to a lower energy state if the salinity could be transferred to the deep ocean, or equally, the relatively fresh DOW could be transferred to the surface, independent of its temperature. Such a transfer should thus run as a spontaneous process, i. e., without any energy input to the system. If a vertical pipe is deployed in such an ocean region and filled with DOW once, the cold DOW in the pipe will eventually be heated by the surrounding water while retaining its low salinity. The water column inside the pipe will thus become buoyant with respect to the surrounding water, and a convective upward flow in the pipe will be initiated. Once a steady state of this process is reached, the flow will continue without any external energy input (except ambient heat). Stommel et al. (1956) were the first to describe this effect, naming it the *perpetual salt fountain*. The effect is conceptually linked to double-diffusive convection, a well-known feature in oceanic flow, with the difference that here, the diffusion of salt is not only smaller than the heat diffusion but entirely suppressed due to the presence of the pipe wall. It is worth noting that in the same ocean regions, Stommel’s effect can also be used to drive downwelling instead of upwelling if the pipe is initially filled with surface water instead of DOW. Since its publication, several device concepts have been proposed on the basis of this principle. In the present work, we will summarize these device concepts under the term Stommel Upwelling Pipe (SUP).

Engineered transport of DOW to the surface ocean is known as Artificial Upwelling (AU). This process has been studied in numerous contexts (Stommel et al., 1956; Liu and Jin, 1995; Takahashi, 2000; Kirke, 2003; Liang and Peng, 2005; Kithil, 2006). Most proposals target DOW for its high inorganic nutrient concentrations, which are utilized to enable biological primary production in the surface ocean. Recently, AU has received new scientific interest due to its potential to enhance oceanic CO₂ uptake and thus act as a marine Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) measure (Lovelock and Rapley, 2007; Dutreuil et al., 2009; Yool et al., 2009; Oschlies et al., 2010; Keller et al., 2014; Koweek, 2022; Jürchott et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023). While the salt fountain effect was initially introduced as a curiosity rather than a practical engineering concept Stommel et al. (1956), SUP systems have several advantageous properties for driving large-scale deployments of AU. Based on the fact that no external energy supply is required to drive SUP systems and their construction can be comparably simple (no moving parts), SUP systems could represent an enabling technology for large-scale AU-based CDR in the open ocean, provided they have the potential to upwell significant volumes of DOW.

Several authors have tried to quantify and demonstrate the potential of SUP systems. A first effort to quantify possible flow rates has been undertaken by Groves (1958). Groves studied a simple ocean profile using an analytical method. He analyzed his results in the context of fish-farm fertilization but concluded that SUP-based fertilization with DOW was not likely to be economically interesting due to the low flow

46 rates. Hinman (1966) extended Groves's calculations, with the addition of vertical
 47 heat transfer and a numerical implementation. Even though Hinman found the effect
 48 of vertical heat transfer to be negligible, he found considerably larger upwelling flow
 49 rates than Groves by using different ocean depth profile data and pipe setups. Johnson
 50 and Decicco (1983) proposed a new type of SUP device, where downwelling, based
 51 on the salt fountain principle, is established in a number of tubes running through an
 52 outer shell where upwelling is established. Using a simplified analytical model, John-
 53 son and Decicco showed that their concept could be upscaled to achieve flow rates
 54 of $1.32 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. A first successful prototype test of Stommel's concept was reported by
 55 Maruyama et al. (2004). Using a flexible 0.3 m diameter, 280 m long pipe, Maruyama
 56 et al. were able to achieve an upwelling flow rate of $1.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. In a further field ex-
 57 periment, upwelling of $5.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was achieved (Tsubaki et al., 2007). The results
 58 of Maruyama et al. (2004) were subsequently extended with numerical simulations, us-
 59 ing a Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equation model in laminar mode and
 60 with a fixed uniform eddy viscosity. As the laminar model simulations resulted in poor
 61 agreement with the observations, Maruyama et al. (2004) suggest that wave action on
 62 the surface buoy of their system might have caused turbulent flow in the pipe. Studies
 63 of Zhang et al. (2006) strengthen this explanation.

64 Based on the above literature review, three types of proposed SUP systems are
 65 defined in the present work. The three types are schematically shown in Figure 1.
 66 In the following, they will be referred to as single SUP (sSUP), counterflow SUP (cSUP),
 67 and shell-and-tube type SUP (satSUP). While strictly the cSUP concept marks a special
 68 case of a satSUP system with a single inner pipe, it is treated as a separate concept
 69 throughout this work for its special geometric properties. It should be noted that in
 70 contrast to Johnson and Decicco (1983), who initially proposed this device type, in the
 71 present work the inner pipe of cSUP and satSUP systems is the upwelling pipe while
 72 downwelling is considered in the outer shell. This allows a more direct comparison
 between the system types.

Figure 1: Basic types of SUP systems

73 Table 1 summarizes the previous studies on the performance of SUP systems. As
 74

Study	Pipe dimensions ($L \times D$) [m]	Concept	Method	Region	Upwelling velocity [m/s]
Groves (1958)	600×0.2	sSUP	1D model	n.a.	0.175
Hinman (1966)	$175 - 600 \times 0.2 - 0.4$	sSUP	1D model	generic	0.163 - 0.336
Johnson and Decicco (1983)	$500 \times 0.1 / 500 \times 0.05$ ^a	satSUP	1D model	Florida / Chile	0.116 / 0.037
Maruyama et al. (2004)	280×0.3	sSUP	Experiment	Mariana Trench	2.45×10^{-3}
Tsubaki et al. (2007)	300×0.3	sSUP	Experiment	Mariana Islands	7.5×10^{-3}

^a Here, the inner pipe dimensions are given as a reference even though Johnson and Decicco propose the upwelling flow to be on the shell side.

Table 1: Results of previous studies on SUP systems

75 can be seen here, sSUP and satSUP systems of varying sizes have previously been
76 studied, mostly using simple one-dimensional pipe flow models and typically resulting
77 in upwelling velocities between 0.1 m/s and 0.2 m/s . A substantial discrepancy between
78 the SUP performance from model predictions and experimental observations is evi-
79 dent in Table 1. This discrepancy, despite perhaps being mostly driven by the choice
80 of deployment region for the field experiments, introduces a large uncertainty to the
81 overall range of expected SUP performances and, thus, to the present understanding
82 of the potential of these systems for AU. Additionally, the low upwelling velocities
83 observed in the field experiments mean that the corresponding data can hardly be used
84 to validate new SUP performance prediction methods. To overcome this situation and
85 provide reliable SUP performance predictions in the absence of full-scale validation
86 data, the present work focuses on a combination of model validation studies for indi-
87 vidual well-studied flow phenomena essential to SUP performance as well as model
88 intercomparison efforts for different SUP types and ocean conditions. We introduce a
89 new one-dimensional pipe flow model and a RANS model for SUP simulations. While
90 the RANS model enables high-fidelity studies of arbitrary SUP geometries and also
91 allows for validation with respect to specific flow phenomena, the one-dimensional
92 model is directly based on pipe flow theory and enables extensive studies due to its low
93 computational cost. The consistency of both models in predicting key aspects of SUP
94 performance is demonstrated in this work and some remaining model uncertainties are
95 evaluated and quantified.

96 1.1. Mixed convection

97 The self-sustaining flow in a SUP system is driven by the interaction of two ef-
98 fects, the hydrostatic pressure head and the heat transfer through the pipe wall. These
99 two effects are conceptually linked to two basic flow regimes in thermal fluid dynam-
100 ics, with distinctly different characteristics, namely forced and natural convection. For
101 most thermal fluid dynamics problems, either forced or natural convection predomi-
102 nates whereas the other component can be safely neglected. For typical SUP systems,
103 such simplifications cannot be made as will be shown later. SUP systems thus typically
104 exhibit mixed-convection flow, i. e., a flow regime in which neither natural-convection
105 nor forced-convection effects are negligible. A classification of the flow regime can
106 generally be made based on the Richardson number ($Ri = Gr/Re^2$). Flows with $Ri < 0.1$

107 are typically viewed as forced convection, while flows with $Ri > 10$ correspond to nat-
 108 ural convection. Richardson numbers between these values are associated with mixed
 109 convection.

110 For flow in vertical passages and pipes, mixed-convection effects are known to scale
 111 with a dimensionless buoyancy parameter, which is defined as

$$112 \quad Bo = \frac{Gr^*}{Re^{3.425} Pr^{0.8}}, \quad (1)$$

113 where Gr^* is the heat flux-based Grashof number, Re is the Reynolds number, and Pr
 114 is the Prandtl number.

115 Figure 2 shows typical flow profiles in a vertical pipe for forced convection as well
 116 as different degrees of buoyancy influence. While natural and forced convection ex-
 117 hibit defined mean flow, shear, and turbulence production patterns, mixed convection
 118 is characterized by a complex nonlinear interaction of these patterns, with correspond-
 119 ing changes in laminar-turbulent transition behavior, heat transfer, and wall friction
 120 (Jackson et al., 1989). In the buoyancy-aided¹ case of laminar mixed convection, heat
 121 transfer in a vertical pipe is generally enhanced, i. e., Nusselt numbers are observed to
 122 be higher than the forced-convection values at the same Reynolds number. However,
 123 in the turbulent buoyancy-aided case, the heat transfer shows a nonlinear behavior. As
 124 described by Jackson et al. (1989), the heat transfer is significantly impaired when the
 125 buoyancy influence is small ($2 \times 10^{-6} < Bo < 2 \times 10^{-5}$), and enhanced as buoyancy
 126 effects become dominant ($Bo > 2 \times 10^{-5}$). This nonlinear behavior is schematically
 127 depicted in Figure 3. Here, the Nusselt number is normalized by its forced-convection
 128 value such that values below unity reflect heat transfer impairment, while higher values
 129 represent heat transfer enhancement due to buoyancy effects.

Figure 2: Turbulent pipe velocity profiles for different degrees of buoyancy influence

Figure 3: Buoyancy-aided mixed-convection effects on the heat transfer efficiency in turbulent pipe flow

130 To the authors' knowledge, mixed-convection effects have not been considered in

¹Mixed convection can either be buoyancy-aided (e. g., upward flow through a heated pipe or downward flow through a cooled pipe) or buoyancy-opposed (e. g., downward flow through a heated pipe). In this work, only the buoyancy-aided case is considered, since buoyancy-opposed mixed convection is not relevant for SUP systems.

131 previous SUP studies, despite their potentially significant impact on SUP performance
132 predictions. In this work, special emphasis is thus put on the correct reproduction of
133 mixed-convection effects.

134 1.2. Outline

135 The remainder of this work is structured as follows: First, two numerical methods
136 for predicting SUP performance are described in Section 2 and validated, where pos-
137 sible. Additionally, common SUP geometries and ocean profiles are defined for the
138 subsequent studies. In Section 3, results from studies on several aspects of SUP per-
139 formance are presented, discussed, and compared between both methods. Conclusions
140 from the results are drawn in Section 4.

141 2. Numerical methods

142 In this section, two numerical methods for SUP systems are introduced, namely
143 a RANS model, which will be referred to as the *ocean4Foam* (*o4F*) method (Kemper,
144 2024, version a5f80c2c), and a one-dimensional model, which will be referred to as the
145 *SPID* (short for *Stommel-Pipe one-dimensional*) method (Kemper and Mense, 2024,
146 version db0309a3). Preceding implementations of both methods have been described
147 by Kemper et al. (2023) as work in progress. Here, the revised model equations of
148 both methods are described in detail, and their discretization and solution are outlined.
149 Verification and validation of the *ocean4Foam* method is carried out as indicated in
150 Section 1. Finally, a benchmark case setup consisting of geometry information and
151 ocean data is defined.

152 2.1. The *ocean4Foam* method

153 The RANS model used in this work is developed as part of the *ocean4Foam* tool-
154 box. It implements the oceanic Boussinesq set of RANS equations (Young, 2010),
155 using the OpenFOAM[®] environment. The oceanic Boussinesq approximation was de-
156 scribed by Young (2010) as three steps:

- 157 1. The exact density ρ in the momentum equation is replaced by a constant refer-
158 ence density ρ_0 everywhere but in the buoyancy term.
- 159 2. The incompressible continuity equation $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ is used.
- 160 3. An equation of state of the form $\rho = f(\overline{S}_A, \overline{\Theta}, P_0 + \rho_0 \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is used, where $\overline{\Theta}$ is
161 the conservative temperature of McDougall (2003), \overline{S}_A is absolute salinity, P_0 is
162 the reference pressure at the water surface, ρ_0 is a constant reference density, \mathbf{g}
163 is the gravitational acceleration vector, and \mathbf{r} is the position vector with respect
164 to a reference position at the water surface.

165 The oceanic Boussinesq set of RANS equations, as implemented in the *ocean4Foam*
 166 method, reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}} \bar{\mathbf{u}}) &= \nabla \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^* - \nabla \bar{p}_{gh}^* + \mathbf{g} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} - 1 \right) \\
 \nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}} &= 0 \\
 \frac{\partial \bar{\Theta}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}} \bar{\Theta}) &= \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla \bar{\Theta} - \bar{\Theta} \mathbf{u}) \\
 \frac{\partial \bar{S}_A}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}} \bar{S}_A) &= \nabla \cdot (D \nabla \bar{S}_A - \bar{S}_A \mathbf{u}) \\
 \rho &= f(\bar{S}_A, \bar{\Theta}, p_0 + \rho_0 \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

168 In Equation (2), t is time and $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ is the velocity vector. The tensor $\bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^*$ denotes the devia-
 169 toric part of the effective, kinematic Reynolds stress tensor

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^* = 2\nu_e \bar{\mathbf{S}} - \frac{2}{3}\nu_e (\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}}) \mathbf{I}, \tag{3}$$

171 where ν_e is the effective viscosity, which includes laminar diffusion and the modeling
 172 of turbulence effects ($\nu_e = \nu + \nu_t$), and $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ is the mean strain rate tensor (see nomenclature
 173 for details). The modified kinematic pressure \bar{p}_{gh}^* in Equation (2) is calculated from the
 174 static pressure as $\bar{p}_{gh}^* = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \bar{P} - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \frac{2}{3}k$, with k being the turbulent kinetic energy. The
 175 molecular diffusivities of temperature and salinity are denoted λ and D in Equation (2),
 176 while the terms $\bar{\Theta} \mathbf{u}$ and $\bar{S}_A \mathbf{u}$ represent the respective turbulent fluxes. Typically, these
 177 fluxes are modeled using the Simple Gradient Diffusion Hypothesis (SGDH), whereby
 178 the right-hand side of the $\bar{\Theta}$ equation becomes

$$\nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla \bar{\Theta} - \bar{\Theta} \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\lambda_e \nabla \bar{\Theta}) = \nabla \cdot \left(\left(\lambda + \frac{\nu_t}{\sigma_t} \right) \nabla \bar{\Theta} \right), \tag{4}$$

180 with σ_t being the turbulent Prandtl number. (The S_A equation is treated in the same
 181 way.) Alternative scalar flux models are available within *ocean4Foam* as well as mod-
 182 els for non-constant turbulent Prandtl numbers. These aspects will be discussed in
 183 Section 2.3 along with the choice of the turbulence model.

184 The seawater properties are modeled using the method of McDougall et al. (2003)
 185 for ρ (following the *TEOS-10* standard (IOC et al., 2010)) and the polynomials of
 186 Sharqawy et al. (2010) and Jamieson and Tudhope (1970) for ν and λ , respectively.

187 The fundamental equations (Equation (2)) are discretized using the finite volume
 188 method and implemented as a solver using the OpenFOAM[®] environment. OpenFOAM[®]'s
 189 *PIMPLE* algorithm (a transient version of the well-known *SIMPLE* algorithm) is em-
 190 ployed to solve the coupled equation set in a pressure-based manner. The following
 191 numerical schemes are used: Gradients are discretized using the Gauss method with
 192 linear interpolation. For the convective terms in the momentum and scalar transport
 193 equations, linear upwind and limited linear schemes are employed, respectively. A
 194 pseudo-transient approach is used for temporal discretization, which was observed to

195 be numerically more stable and converge to the final solution much faster than a steady-
 196 state simulation process. Due to the use of the pseudo-transient approach, only converged
 197 steady-state solutions are given in this work, and no data on the initial transient
 198 development of the flow inside a SUP system is generated.

199 2.2. The SPID method

200 The one-dimensional method described in this section is based on considerations
 201 of hydrostatic balance as well as pipe flow formulations for pressure loss and heat
 202 transfer. The method is one-dimensional in the sense that variations of the field vari-
 203 ables are only resolved along the axial z coordinate (positive down). Consequently, the
 204 state variables conservative temperature (Θ), absolute salinity (S_A), and pressure (P)
 205 at each vertical position represent bulk values, and the fluid properties are evaluated
 206 with respect to these values. The primary aim of the method is to predict the unknown
 207 upwelling velocity w along with the variation of the state variables for any given SUP
 208 geometry and background ocean profile.

209 The basic equations of the *SPID* method are equal for sSUP, cSUP, and satSUP
 210 systems. The equations are thus introduced in a generalized form. Differences between
 211 the formulations for different SUP types are pointed out where necessary and a full
 212 description is given in Appendix A.

213 The first equation represents a pressure balance between the hydrostatic pressure
 214 head and the dynamic pressure loss for a fully developed steady-state flow

$$215 \quad c_f \frac{\hat{\rho}}{2} \frac{w^2}{D_h} L = g \left| \int_{z_{top}}^{z_{top}+L} (\rho_{ocean}(z) - \rho(z)) dz \right|. \quad (5)$$

216 Here, w is the upwelling velocity, c_f is the corresponding Darcy pipe friction factor, D_h
 217 is the hydraulic pipe diameter (see Appendix A for details), and g is the gravitational
 218 acceleration. Further, ρ and ρ_{ocean} are the density of the water inside the pipe and the
 219 background ocean, respectively, while $\hat{\rho}$ is the average density over the pipe length.
 220 The density of seawater is calculated from the equation of state

$$221 \quad \rho = f(S_A, \Theta, P). \quad (6)$$

222 The background ocean values Θ_{ocean} and $S_{A,ocean}$ are known functions of z . Since the
 223 salinity is not changed inside the SUP system, S_A uniformly takes the value of the flow
 224 entering the pipe. Knowledge of the temperature profile $\Theta(z)$ inside the pipe would
 225 thus enable us to rearrange Equation (5) and calculate the unknown upwelling velocity
 226 w at this point. (The hydrostatic pressure is used for P in Equation (6).)

227 The temperature profile can be obtained by solving the following ordinary differ-
 228 ential equation over the interval (z_{top}, z_{bottom}) , using the known inlet temperature as
 229 boundary condition

$$230 \quad -A_c w \hat{\rho} c_p(z) \Theta'(z) + C_h U(z) (\Theta_{ot}(z) - \Theta(z)) = 0. \quad (7)$$

231 Physically this equation represents a balance between convective heat transfer in the
 232 axial direction and radial conductive heat transfer through the pipe wall. Here, A_c is

233 the cross-sectional area of the pipe, C_h is the heat-transferring circumference, c_p is
 234 the heat capacity and Θ_{ot} refers to the temperature of the fluid on the other side of
 235 the pipe wall. Hence, Θ_{ot} is the background ocean temperature in the case of a sSUP
 236 system, the shell-side value when the equation is solved for the inner pipe of a cSUP or
 237 satSUP system, and the inner-pipe value when Equation (7) is solved for the shell-side
 238 flow. The coefficient U in Equation (7) represents an overall heat transfer coefficient,
 239 which incorporates the thermal resistance of the pipe wall as well as the influence
 240 of the convection on either side of the wall. The three components of U depend on
 241 the respective thermal conductivities κ and Nusselt numbers N_D (see Appendix A for
 242 details).

243 With correlations for the pipe friction factor, the Nusselt number, and the fluid
 244 properties¹, the system of Equations (5) and (7) is closed for a given pipe geometry
 245 and ocean profile (Θ_{ocean} and $S_{A_{ocean}}$). For sSUP systems, only the coupling between
 246 Equations (5) and (7) has to be solved. This coupling is handled using the iterative pro-
 247 cess depicted in Figure 4. For cSUP and satSUP systems, the two balances (Equation
 248 (5) and Equation (7)) have to be solved for both, the inner pipe² and the shell. As the
 249 two sides are coupled via the temperature difference in Equation (7), a system of four
 250 coupled equations is obtained. Again, the process depicted in Figure 4 is followed to
 251 solve this system of equations. The two instances of Equation (7) (for the inner pipe
 252 and shell) are solved as a coupled boundary value problem in each iteration, using a
 collocation algorithm.

Figure 4: Flow diagram of the *SPID* solution algorithm

253
 254

Several general points about the previously described set of equations for SUP sys-

¹In this work, the *TEOS-10* IOC et al. (2010) standard is used for ρ and c_p , while κ is calculated using the method of Jamieson and Tudhope (1970).

²One representative inner pipe is solved in the case of satSUP systems.

255 tems should be noted: Equation (7) describes a mere balance of vertical heat convection
 256 and horizontal heat conduction. Other energy forms, as well as vertical heat conduc-
 257 tion, are not considered here³. Additionally, as for cSUP and satSUP systems, Equation
 258 (7) only balances the heat transfer between inner-pipe and shell-side flow, any possible
 259 heat transfer between the shell-side flow and background ocean (i. e., through the outer
 260 pipe wall) is not taken into account. The negligence of the outer pipe heat transfer for
 261 cSUP and satSUP systems largely simplifies the definition of the equations and enables
 262 the generic formulation for different SUP types. From an engineering point of view, the
 263 negligence of the outer pipe heat transfer can be justified by the fact that the outer pipe
 264 wall will usually have to provide structural stability to the SUP system and will thus
 265 likely have a considerably higher wall thickness than the inner pipe(s). To quantify the
 266 effect of this simplification, outer pipe heat transfer is studied for a cSUP system in
 267 Section 3.3, using the *ocean4Foam* method.

268 The empirical coefficients, namely the Nusselt number N_D and the Darcy friction
 269 factor c_f , largely affect the solutions of the *SPID* method. Little has previously been
 270 published on the correct formulation of the corresponding correlations for SUP sys-
 271 tems. The determination of these factors is significantly complicated by the fact that
 272 the flow in SUP systems can be laminar, transitional, or turbulent and dominated by
 273 forced, natural, and mixed convection. Also, extreme off-equilibrium states during the
 274 convergence of the solution process have to be reproduced at least qualitatively cor-
 275 rectly. Since empirical correlations are usually only formulated for one combination of
 276 turbulence and convection regime, blending between different formulations or their use
 277 outside of the intended range of applicability can hardly be avoided. In the following,
 278 an engineering approach is described to obtain c_f and N_D across the entire range of
 279 relevant flow regimes.

280 The correlation of Morrison (2013) is invariably used for c_f . It reads

$$281 \quad c_f = 4 \left(\frac{0.0076 \left(\frac{3170}{Re} \right)^{0.165}}{1 + \left(\frac{3170}{Re} \right)^7} + \frac{16}{Re} \right). \quad (8)$$

282 This correlation is valid for forced-convection pipe flow across the entire Reynolds
 283 number range up to 1×10^6 . A consistent formulation for mixed and natural convection
 284 was not pursued in the course of this work, due to the lack of established correlations
 285 for these flow regimes.

286 The Nusselt number N_D is determined by first calculating the laminar and turbulent
 287 forced-convection values and then applying the respective mixed-convection correc-
 288 tions. The laminar and turbulent values are then blended in the case of transitional
 289 flow. The forced convection value for both, the laminar and turbulent regime is calcu-
 290 lated following Gnielinski (2010a) and Gnielinski (2010b) for cylindrical pipes (sSUP
 291 and inner pipe of cSUP) and annular pipes (shell of cSUP), respectively. In the lam-
 292 inar case, the mixed-convection correction is calculated following Behzadmehr et al.
 293 (2003). While the correlation of Behzadmehr et al. (2003) was initially proposed for

³Vertical heat conduction in SUP systems has been studied by Hinman (1966), who found a negligible effect on the overall flow rate.

294 a small Re range, it remains consistent with commonly used formulations for laminar
 295 forced convection and is thus used for the entire laminar range here. The complexity
 296 of turbulent mixed convection has already been discussed in Section 1.1. A semi-
 297 empirical model to describe the behavior depicted in Figure 3 has been formulated by
 298 Jackson et al. (1989). This correlation reads

$$299 \quad N_D/N_{Df} = \left| 1 - c \frac{Bo}{(a N_D/N_{Df} - b)^2} \right|^n. \quad (9)$$

300 The factor c is 8×10^4 for the cylindrical pipes and 1.25×10^5 for annular pipes⁴ (Jack-
 301 son et al., 1989; Kim et al., 2002). While Jackson et al. (1989) initially proposed a , b ,
 302 and n to be 1, 0, and 0.46, respectively, Nguyen et al. (2023) recently proposed a de-
 303 viation from this simple formulation. Based on extensive DNS studies, Nguyen et al.
 304 (2023) suggest the coefficients given in Table 2 for Equation (9). This formulation is
 used throughout the present work. The laminar forced and mixed-convection formu-

	$c Bo \leq 0.26$	$c Bo > 0.26$
a	0.56	1.78
b	0.35	0.50
n	0.56	2.03

Table 2: Coefficients for Equation (9) following Nguyen et al. (2023)

305
 306 lations are applied when $Re < 2300$ and $Gr^* < 5 \times 10^7$. The turbulent formulations
 307 are applied when $Re > 4000$ or when $Gr^* > 5 \times 10^8$. In the transition regions, linear
 308 blending is applied as suggested by Gnielinski (1995). As the turbulent formulation is
 309 applied across the entire Re range if $Gr^* > 5 \times 10^8$, the Re value used in the calcula-
 310 tions is limited to a minimum of 4000 in these situations to account for the fact that the
 311 Nusselt number becomes independent of Re under low-flow conditions (Rouai, 1987).

312 For lack of specialized correlations, the formulations for annular pipes are also
 313 applied to the shell side flow of satSUP systems. Kemper et al. (2023) have tested this
 314 procedure against RANS calculations of satSUP systems and generally found good
 315 agreement of the results.

316 As the convection outside of the pipe wall of sSUP systems (i. e., in the background
 317 ocean) marks an external natural-convection flow, the corresponding Nusselt number
 318 is treated separately. Here, the well-known correlation of Churchill and Chu (1975) is
 319 applied. Note that the assumption of pure natural convection in the background ocean
 320 is representative of a theoretical situation with no current. Since cross-flow generally
 321 increases the heat transfer from a vertical cylinder, this is a conservative assumption
 322 for sSUP performance.

323 2.3. Verification and validation

324 In the absence of full-scale validation data for SUP systems, validation of SUP
 325 performance prediction methods has to be carried out for well-studied flow phenomena

⁴for annular pipes N_D/N_{Df} is limited to values greater than 0.75, which is in line with the experimental results of Kim et al. (2002). For details see Section 2.3.

326 that are relevant to SUP performance. Such validation efforts can only be carried out
 327 for the *ocean4Foam* method. In this section, the *ocean4Foam* method is validated for
 328 forced and mixed-convection flow of seawater in cylindrical and annular pipes.

329 A case setup with a simple, two-dimensional pipe mesh is used. The diameter is
 330 0.15 m for the cylindrical pipe, while for the annular pipe, the inner and outer diameters
 331 are 0.15 m and 0.26 m, respectively. The height of the simulated section is 0.15 m.
 332 To obtain a fully developed flow field in the section, cyclic boundary conditions are
 333 used at the inlet and outlet for velocity and turbulent quantities. For temperature, a
 334 modified cyclic boundary condition is used, such that a constant mean value of 15 °C
 335 is maintained at the inlet. The salinity is constant and uniform at 35.5 g/kg in the modeled
 336 section. A uniform pressure gradient is applied and automatically adjusted to maintain
 337 a set mean velocity in the pipe, thus controlling the Reynolds number. A uniform heat
 338 flux is applied at the pipe wall. For the annular pipe, only the inner wall is heated, while
 339 the outer wall is adiabatic. This setup allows for the buoyancy parameter Bo (Equation
 340 1) to be systematically varied, which is done here by keeping Re at a constant value of
 341 8000 and varying the wall heat flux.

342 First, a grid independence verification is carried out by systematically varying the
 343 number of cells across the radial dimension (N_x). Throughout this study, a constant cell
 344 size is maintained at the pipe wall(s) ($y^+ = 0.25$) for all N_x values. This is achieved by
 345 applying different gradual refinements in the radial direction. The study is performed
 346 for forced convection ($Bo = 1 \times 10^{-7}$). The results are shown in Figure 5 along with
 347 a regression analysis and the 1% error threshold with respect to the extrapolated exact
 solution (at $1/N_x = 0$). As can be seen from the regression analysis, the rate of

Figure 5: Grid independence study. Nusselt number over the reciprocal of the radial cell count N_x . *ocean4Foam* results are given along with a regression analysis and the 1% error threshold.

348 convergence closely reflects the theoretical value for a second-order method (i. e., an
 349 exponent of 2). For all further studies, a value of 50 cells across the radial dimension
 350 ($1/N_x = 0.02$) is chosen for the cylindrical pipe, while 70 cells ($1/N_x = 0.014$) are used
 351 for the annular Pipe. This choice ensures discretization errors below 1%, as shown in
 352 Figure 5.
 353

354 Having verified the numerical setup, the validation study can now be carried out us-

355 ing different turbulence and scalar flux modeling approaches implemented in *ocean4Foam*.
 356 As shown by Keshmiri et al. (2012), the choice of turbulence model can have a signifi-
 357 cant effect on the reproduction of heat transfer for mixed-convection flows. Of several
 358 turbulence models examined in their studies, Keshmiri et al. (2012) found the v^2 - f
 359 model (Durbin, 1991) to achieve the best overall agreement with LES and DNS results
 360 as well as experimental data. With the k - ϵ - ϕ_t - f turbulence model of Laurence et al.
 361 (2005), OpenFOAM[®] implements a version of the v^2 - f model which aims to be code-
 362 friendly and more numerically stable than the original formulation. The k - ϵ - ϕ_t - f model
 363 is thus tested here along with the well-known k - ω SST turbulence model (Menter,
 364 1994). The turbulent thermal fluxes have been modeled using the SGDH (Equation
 365 (4)) with a constant turbulent Prandtl number σ_t in most previous RANS studies on
 366 mixed convection (Keshmiri et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2008). Models for non-constant
 367 σ_t values (Reynolds, 1975) and other scalar flux modeling options (Daly and Harlow,
 368 1970; Kenjereš et al., 2005; Younis et al., 2005) have been widely discussed in the lit-
 369 erature for different applications. Recently, Irrenfried and Steiner (2017) have found σ_t
 370 values from DNS calculations of heated pipe flow to increasingly deviate from a con-
 371 stant value as molecular Prandtl numbers exceed unity. These results suggest that for
 372 our work, which uses seawater ($Pr \approx 8.2$) as the working fluid, non-standard models
 373 for the turbulent thermal flux may have to be used. The SGDH with $\sigma_t = 0.9$ was thus
 374 tested against the variable σ_t model of Kays and Crawford (1993) (hereafter referred
 375 to as KC) and the algebraic flux model of Kenjereš et al. (2005) (hereafter referred to
 376 as AFM). The KC model gives the turbulent Prandtl number as

$$377 \quad \sigma_t^{-1} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_{t\infty}} + C \frac{\nu_t}{\nu} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sigma_{t\infty}}} - \left(C \frac{\nu_t}{\nu} \right)^2 \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{C \frac{\nu_t}{\nu} \sqrt{\sigma_{t\infty}}} \right) \right], \quad (10)$$

378 where $\sigma_{t\infty} = 0.85$ and $C = 0.21$. We found that for seawater the predicted σ_t values
 379 are in acceptable agreement with the DNS results of Irrenfried and Steiner (2017). For
 380 the sake of brevity, the AFM model of Kenjereš et al. (2005) will not be explained here
 381 in detail. In contrast to the previously described options, this model is directly derived
 382 from the second-moment closure equations for the turbulent thermal flux $\overline{\Theta u}$ and thus
 383 entirely avoids the use of the SGDH.

384 Figure 6 shows the Nusselt number predicted by the different model configurations
 385 over a Bo variation from 1×10^{-7} (forced convection) to 2×10^{-4} . The results for
 386 the cylindrical pipe are compared against the correlations of Jackson et al. (1989) and
 387 Nguyen et al. (2023) as well as three DNS data points of You et al. (2003). For the an-
 388 nular pipe, the correlation of Kim et al. (2002) is given along with a modified version
 389 of the Nguyen et al. (2023) correlation, which was adopted to the annular geometry
 390 following Kim et al. (2002). All results are normalized by the theoretical forced-
 391 convection value, which was calculated using Gnielinski's correlations (Gnielinski,
 392 2010a,b). It can be seen that the constant σ_t results have a significant offset to the
 393 theory and data. The k - ω SST model is generally found to predict the heat transfer
 394 impairment due to the onset of mixed convection at higher Bo values than the k - ϵ - ϕ_t - f
 395 model. This is consistent with the poor performance of the k - ω SST model found by
 396 Keshmiri et al. (2012). Both, the KC and AFM models perform much better than the
 397 constant σ_t model. Both models predict the correct forced-convection Nusselt number

Figure 6: Normalized Nusselt number over Buoyancy number for cylindrical and annular pipe case. Results from the *ocean4Foam* model using different turbulence and turbulent thermal flux modeling approaches, along with appropriate empirical correlations as well as DNS data of You et al. (2003). For the cylindrical pipe, the correlations of Jackson et al. (1989) and Nguyen et al. (2023) are plotted, while for the annular pipe, the correlation of Kim et al. (2002) and a correspondingly modified version of the Nguyen et al. (2023) correlation are shown.

398 (within 3 % error). For the annular pipe, the heat transfer impairment is predicted by
 399 *ocean4Foam* to be less pronounced and with a less sudden onset. This is in line with
 400 the experimental data of Kim et al. (2002) but not represented by their theory, which
 401 Kim et al. (2002) adopted from the cylindrical pipe. To better adjust the theory to the
 402 data, the correlation for the annular pipe is limited to a minimum value of 0.75 in the
 403 implementation of the *SPID* method.

404 To further demonstrate the validity for the forced convection case ($Bo = 1 \times 10^{-7}$),
 405 w^+ and Θ^+ profiles across the pipe radius are shown in Figure 7. The results are com-
 406 pared against DNS data of Irrenfried and Steiner (2017) and the theoretical solutions
 407 for the viscous sublayer and logarithmic region⁵. Only the results for the cylindrical
 408 pipe are shown. Figure 7 additionally shows results from a calculation with a constant
 409 tuned value of $\sigma_t = 1.35$ which produces the correct Nusselt number. It is evident
 410 from Figure 7 that both the KC and AFM models, in combination with the $k-\epsilon-\phi_t-f$ tur-
 411 bulence model, ensure correct scaling of the velocity and temperature across the pipe
 412 diameter. The same is not found to be the case for the tuned constant turbulent Prandtl
 413 number. These results confirm the adequacy of the non-standard thermal flux models
 414 for the present case. For all further calculations in this work, the KC model is used.
 415 While arguably providing less generality, the KC model provides a numerically more
 416 stable and cost-effective alternative to the AFM approach.

⁵Following Irrenfried and Steiner (2017), the coefficients $\kappa = 0.34$, $B = 0.45$, and $\sigma_t = 0.9$ are used for the logarithmic law of the wall. The function of Jayatilke (1969) is used for P .

Figure 7: Radial profiles of axial velocity (a) and temperature (b) in wall units. Results from the *ocean4Foam* model using different turbulent thermal flux modeling approaches, along with DNS data of Irrenfried and Steiner (2017) and theory. The Θ^+ results of Irrenfried and Steiner (2017) are given for molecular Prandtl numbers of 1 and 10. The Prandtl number in the present case is 8.2.

417 **2.4. Benchmark geometry**

418 Benchmark SUP geometries are used for all further studies in this work. The ge-
 419 ometries are developed based on considerations of technical feasibility, comparability,
 420 and good general upwelling performance. They do not represent optimized setups in
 any sense. Figure 8 shows both setups and their main dimensions. Both setups have a

Figure 8: Benchmark geometry for sSUP (left) and cSUP (right) system

421

422 bottom depth of 400 m, a top depth of 5 m, and a (inner) pipe diameter of 0.15 m. For
 423 the cSUP setup, the outer pipe diameter is obtained from the inner-to-outer-pipe cross-
 424 sectional flow area ratio, which is set to 0.5. The thickness and thermal conductivity
 425 of the (inner) pipe wall were chosen such that the thermal resistivity equates to $s/\kappa_{wall} =$
 426 $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K m}^2/\text{W}$. This corresponds to a HDPE pipe with $s = 1 \text{ mm}$ or a steel pipe with s
 427 $= 90 \text{ mm}$.

428 The *ocean4Foam* calculations are set up using two-dimensional axisymmetrical
 429 pipe meshes (i. e., only the axial and radial directions are resolved). Only the fluid
 430 domain inside the pipe is resolved by the *ocean4Foam* calculations, whereas the back-
 431 ground ocean is considered through boundary conditions. This choice is consistent for
 432 the cSUP case with adiabatic outer walls, where the flow outside the pipe has no influ-
 433 ence on the convection inside the pipe. For the sSUP case, the effect of the outside flow
 434 on the wall heat transfer has to be parameterized. For idealized ocean conditions (i. e.,
 435 no currents or waves), this can be conveniently achieved by a convective boundary
 436 condition on the pipe wall, which specifies the local wall temperature Θ_w as

$$437 \quad \Theta_w = f\Theta_{ocean} + (1 - f)\Theta_C, \quad (11)$$

438 where Θ_C is the temperature at the centroid of the grid cell next to the wall and

$$439 \quad f = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\kappa}{h\delta}}. \quad (12)$$

440 Here, δ is the distance from the wall to the nearest cell centroid and the heat transfer
 441 coefficient h is calculated from the Nusselt number using the correlation of Churchill
 442 and Chu (1975)⁶. Arguably, the introduction of a Nusselt number correlation for the
 443 convection outside of the pipe decreases the model fidelity compared to the option
 444 of resolving the outside flow in the calculation. Kemper et al. (2023) compared both
 445 options (i. e., with and without resolved outside flow) and found very little difference,
 446 indicating that the convective boundary condition for sSUP systems can be used with
 447 confidence.

448 In sum, the applied boundary conditions are as follows: All pipe inlets are specified
 449 as total pressure inlets, where the hydrostatic background pressure minus a dynamic
 450 contribution ($0.5 |\mathbf{u}|^2$) is prescribed, and the velocity is calculated from the flux (i. e.,
 451 from the pressure equation). The transported scalar quantities Θ , S_A , and turbulence
 452 quantities are specified based on the background ocean profile. All pipe outlets are
 453 specified as pressure outlets, where the hydrostatic background pressure is prescribed,
 454 along with a Neumann boundary condition for velocity and transported scalar quanti-
 455 ties. On all solid walls, no-slip conditions for velocity are specified together with the
 456 appropriate low-Re values for the turbulence quantities. In the cSUP cases, the outer
 457 pipe wall is adiabatic, and a thermal baffle boundary condition for Θ is applied to the
 458 inner pipe wall, to take care of the heat transfer and thermal wall resistance. In the
 459 sSUP cases, the previously discussed convective boundary condition for Θ is applied
 460 to the pipe wall.

⁶In the implementation, the boundary condition additionally takes into account the thermal resistance of the pipe wall, which leads to a slightly expanded form of Equation 12.

461 For the *ocean4Foam* cases, the radial mesh resolution is chosen as indicated in
 462 Section 2.3, and 4500 cells are used across the pipe length.

463 *2.5. Benchmark ocean profiles*

464 The benchmark ocean profiles presented in this section are meant to provide an
 465 overview of different characteristics of possible SUP deployment regions. With calm
 466 weather conditions, low seasonality, and low biological productivity, the subtropical
 467 ocean gyres often serve as model regions for AU applications. The four large subtropical
 468 ocean gyres, North Atlantic Gyre (NAG), South Atlantic Gyre (SAG), North Pacific Gyre
 469 (NPG), and South Pacific Gyre (SPG) were thus used to derive the benchmark profiles
 470 for this work. We define the extent of the subtropical gyres by the areas enclosed by
 471 the 1.2 g/kg contour of the salinity difference between surface water and DOW at 400 m
 472 depth (i. e., the source depth of the benchmark SUP geometries). With this definition,
 473 four regions with expectably good SUP performance but different depth profile charac-
 474 teristics are obtained. Based on annual mean data for the years 1955 to 2018 from the
 475 Word Ocean Atlas 2018 (Boyer et al., 2018), mean depth profiles for all four regions
 476 were derived. The resulting profiles are shown in Figure 9 along with the extent of the
 four regions.

Figure 9: Definition of subtropical gyres, based on S_A differences between surface and 400 m depth. Annual mean depth profiles for conservative temperature (violet) and absolute salinity (green) for NAG, SAG, NPG, and SPG, with seasonal variation (light colors).

477

478 **3. Results and discussion**

479 In this section, both methods presented in Section 2 are used to predict the perfor-
 480 mance of SUP systems. The presented studies address key aspects of SUP performance
 481 and demonstrate the predictive capabilities of both methods through model intercom-
 482 parison. Additionally, the simplifying model assumption of no heat transfer through
 483 the outer pipe of cSUP and satSUP systems is critically assessed.

484 *3.1. Subtropical gyre study*

485 In this study, results from the two numerical methods are compared for both bench-
 486 mark geometries (cSUP and sSUP) introduced in Section 2.4 and all four benchmark
 487 profiles introduced in Section 2.5. Figure 10 shows the upwelling velocity for the
 cSUP and sSUP system, as obtained by the *ocean4Foam* and the *SPID* method. A first

Figure 10: Upwelling velocity (w) results from both methods for the sSUP and cSUP benchmark geometry and all four benchmark ocean profiles from Section 2.5.

488 reference of SUP performance in the four subtropical gyre regions and the agreement
 489 between the two methods can be obtained from Figure 10. In general, the upwelling
 490 velocities are within the range of previous predictions described in the literature review
 491 (Section 1). The upwelling velocities for the cSUP system are significantly higher than
 492 those for the sSUP system. The results show slightly different dynamics between the
 493 two SUP types. While for the cSUP system, the SAG region clearly shows the highest
 494 potential, the sSUP system performs similarly in all regions except for the NPG region.
 495 These differences are not surprising considering that the temperature profile inside the
 496 sSUP system is highly dependent on the background profile shape, while for the cSUP,
 497 the temperature profile is decoupled from the background ocean to a large extent.
 498

499 The relative differences between the results from both methods are within 12%
 500 for all cases except the cSUP-NPG case. Also, the qualitative agreement between the
 501 two methods is acceptable. Although the number of cases in this study is limited, the
 502 good agreement of the results can be seen as an indication that the effects of different
 503 profile characteristics and device types are reproduced consistently by both methods.
 504 The larger deviation in the cSUP-NPG case will be further studied in Section 3.2.

505 Figure 11 shows the depth profile of the bulk temperature Θ as well as the Nus-
 506 selt number N_D inside the cSUP and sSUP system. The results are only shown for the

Figure 11: Temperature (a) and Nusselt number (b) profiles inside the SUP system (colored) and the background ocean (black) for the SAG case. Results from both methods are shown for the benchmark sSUP and cSUP systems.

507 SAG ocean profile. A close agreement between the Θ and N_D profiles predicted by the
 508 *SPID* and *ocean4Foam* method can be observed for both SUP types. The capability of
 509 the *SPID* method to reproduce the Nusselt numbers variation inside the sSUP system
 510 is remarkable, considering the simplicity of the empirical N_D calculation (see Section
 511 2.2). For the cSUP system, the *SPID* method predicts slightly lower N_D values and
 512 a stronger thermal entrance effect than the *ocean4Foam* method. Despite these differ-
 513 ences, the results shown in Figure 11 indicate that the basic flow phenomena inside
 514 both SUP types are reproduced consistently by the numerical methods.

515 3.2. Pipe diameter study

516 The capability of both methods to realistically reproduce transitions in the flow
 517 regime is evaluated in this study. To study both transitions between forced and natural-
 518 convection-dominated flow, as well as laminar and turbulent flow, the (inner) pipe di-
 519 ameter is systematically varied from 0.05 m to 0.45 m while keeping the other geomet-
 520 ric parameters as described in Section 2.4. Again, all four benchmark ocean profiles
 521 are used, and the study is carried out for both the sSUP and cSUP systems. The results
 522 of this study are presented in Figure 12, which shows the flow velocity w (upwelling
 523 and downwelling), volume flow rate Q , and Nusselt number N_D over the varied diam-
 524 eter for all four benchmark regions. The distribution of the considered cases across
 525 the different flow regimes can be seen in Figure 13, where the results from the *SPID*
 526 method are plotted on a $Gr-Re$ chart.

527 Figure 12 shows that w , Q , and N_D vary significantly with changing diameter. The
 528 upwelling and downwelling velocities generally show a maximum between (inner) pipe
 529 diameters of 0.05 m and 0.2 m with a sharp decline below the optimum value, which
 530 is associated with the laminarization of the flow. Especially the shell-side flow of

Figure 12: Pipe diameter study results. Bulk velocity (w), volume upwelling rate Q , and average Nusselt number N_D over changing diameter. Results from both methods are shown for the sSUP and cSUP (upwelling and downwelling) benchmark geometry and all four benchmark depth profiles.

531 cSUP systems is subject to laminarization, as can be observed in Figure 13. Above the
 532 optimum diameter, the flow velocity typically shows a gradual decline before dropping
 533 suddenly. The comparison with Figure 13 shows that the sudden drop-off in velocity
 534 coincides with the onset of mixed convection. The velocity drop-off is thus likely the
 535 effect of the sudden onset of mixed-convection heat transfer impairment. At larger
 536 diameters, all studied cases show mixed-convection flow, tending to natural convection

Figure 13: Chart of flow regimes for the pipe diameter study results. Only the results of the *SPID* method are shown for the sSUP and cSUP (upwelling and downwelling) benchmark geometry and all four benchmark depth profiles.

537 with increasing (inner) pipe diameter. The flow velocities, as shown in Figure 12,
 538 decrease gradually across this range.

539 The volume flow rate Q consistently increases with the pipe diameter throughout
 540 the studied range, with only small effects due to mixed-convection heat transfer impair-
 541 ment. For N_D , high values are observed in the turbulent forced-convection range with
 542 (inner) pipe diameters of about 0.1 m to 0.2 m, followed by a sharp decline at the onset
 543 of mixed convection and a slow recovery throughout the mixed-convection range. This
 544 is in line with the typical behavior described in Section 1.1.

545 A remarkable agreement between the *SPID* and *ocean4Foam* results is observed in
 546 Figure 12. All qualitative effects are reproduced consistently by both methods. Some
 547 quantitative differences between the *ocean4Foam* and *SPID* solution are observed at
 548 high (inner) pipe diameters. The *SPID* method consistently seems to predict higher val-
 549 ues for w , Q , and N_D in these cases. While this effect could not be entirely explained,
 550 it should be remembered that the Nusselt number calculation for the *SPID* method is
 551 based on a corrected forced-convection value (see Section 2.2). It thus seems plausible
 552 that the method can exhibit inaccuracies if the flow tends towards natural convection.
 553 As expected from the validation studies presented in Section 2.3, the point of onset of
 554 mixed-convection heat transfer impairment is in good agreement between both meth-
 555 ods, with only a small deviation being visible for the cSUP-NPG case at $D = 0.15$ m. It
 556 should be noted that this small difference in the onset of mixed-convection heat trans-
 557 fer impairment is responsible for the deviation in the upwelling velocity observed in
 558 Section 3.1 for the same case.

559 3.3. Outer pipe heat transfer

560 The assumption of no heat transfer with the background ocean through the outer
 561 pipe wall of cSUP systems (i. e., between the shell-side flow and the background ocean)
 562 has been discussed in Section 2.2. While this assumption plays an important role in
 563 formulating the equations of the *SPID* method, it can easily be avoided using the

564 *ocean4Foam* method. Here, the same convective boundary condition as used for the
 565 sSUP cases (see Section 2.4) can be applied to get a simplified model for the outer pipe
 566 heat transfer without having to resolve the background ocean. In this study, the thermal
 567 resistivity of the outer pipe wall is systematically varied from an idealized value of 0
 568 (no resistivity) to 64 times the resistivity of the inner pipe ($R_{inner} = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K m}^2/\text{W}$).
 569 Since the influence is expected to vary based on the background ocean temperature
 570 profile, the study was done for all four benchmark profiles. The geometry and the
 571 thermal resistivity of the inner pipe follow the benchmark cSUP setup from Section
 572 2.4. The results of this study are shown in Figure 14, which depicts the upwelling and
 573 downwelling velocities, normalized by the no-heat-transfer value from Section 3.1,
 over the outer-pipe thermal resistivity, normalized by the inner-pipe value. It can be

Figure 14: Influence of outer pipe heat transfer: Bulk velocity (normalized by the value with no outer pipe heat transfer) over outer pipe thermal resistivity (normalized by the inner pipe value). Upwelling (solid lines) and downwelling velocities (dashed lines) for the benchmark cSUP system are given for all four benchmark depth profiles.

574
 575 seen that the downwelling velocities increase by a factor of up to 2.1 when heat transfer
 576 through the outer pipe is included. The effect on the upwelling velocities is much
 577 smaller. In the NAG and SAG cases, the upwelling velocities increase, while in the
 578 NPG and SPG cases, a slight reduction in upwelling due to outer pipe heat transfer is
 579 possible. This nonuniform effect on the upwelling velocity is caused by a combination
 580 of forced-convection and mixed-convection effects in the shell-side flow. While the in-
 581 creased Reynolds number leads to an increased forced-convection Nusselt number, this
 582 increase is balanced by a corresponding decrease in Bo , which tends to decrease the
 583 Nusselt number (see Figure 3). For the NAG and SAG cases, which generally operate
 584 at lower Bo values, the Re effect dominates and leads to an increased overall heat trans-
 585 fer efficiency, while for the NPG and SPG cases, the deteriorating Bo effect is slightly
 586 more pronounced. An optimized choice of the outer pipe diameter would likely lead to
 587 a significant performance improvement in these cases.

588 Due to the expected structural function of the outer pipe, a higher thermal resistivity
 589 of this pipe seems likely for practical applications. Additionally, the effect of outer pipe
 590 heat transfer can be expected to decrease for satSUP systems with more than one inner
 591 pipe (due to the lower relative surface area). For realistic applications, it thus seems

592 likely that the negligence of outer pipe heat transfer does not lead to an error of more
593 than 10 % in terms of the upwelling velocity, which generally seems to justify this
594 assumption. For setups where the outer pipe has a low thermal resistivity, and perhaps
595 when an exact prediction of the downwelling velocity is of interest, the *SPID* method
596 should be applied with care.

597 **4. Conclusions**

598 In this work, we have introduced and applied two new performance prediction
599 methods for various types of SUP systems. Both methods have been described in detail.
600 While the RANS-based *ocean4Foam* method is subject to a much lower degree of em-
601 pirical assumption and applicable to a wider range of geometries, the one-dimensional
602 *SPID* method runs considerably faster, typically in less than $1/1000$ of the time required
603 by the *ocean4Foam* method. The *SPID* method thus allows for extensive studies while
604 the *ocean4Foam* method enables the investigation of specialized questions (e. g., Sec-
605 tion 3.3).

606 As suitable validation data for SUP systems is not presently available, the versatile
607 *ocean4Foam* method was verified and validated for forced and mixed-convection pipe
608 flow. Throughout this work, we have confirmed in several studies that correct repro-
609 duction of mixed-convection flow phenomena is key for the performance prediction
610 of SUP systems. By comparing the results from both methods for an extensive set of
611 cases involving laminar and turbulent flow as well as forced convection and varying
612 degrees of buoyancy influence, we were able to show that all qualitative phenomena
613 are reproduced with remarkable consistency by the *ocean4Foam* and *SPID* method.

614 In this work, we applied the new methods to cSUP and sSUP systems with varying
615 pipe diameters in several ocean conditions. We generally obtained a higher upwelling
616 performance for cSUP systems. Our results reveal the key flow phenomena relevant
617 to SUP systems while also providing an insight into the range of performance of both
618 SUP types across four subtropical ocean gyres, which are viewed as the most likely
619 deployment regions for SUP-based AU.

620 We additionally assessed the model assumption of no outer pipe heat transfer using
621 the *ocean4Foam* method. Depending on the deployment region, this assumption can
622 lead to an over or underprediction of the upwelling velocity. While the downwelling
623 velocity can be considerably affected by outer pipe heat transfer, the effect on the up-
624 welling velocity is unlikely to exceed 10 % for realistic pipe geometries.

625 Being based on a thorough assessment of the involved flow phenomena as well
626 as rigorous verification, validation, and model intercomparison efforts, the results pre-
627 sented in this work mark a new level of confidence in SUP performance prediction.
628 While the presented values are generally encouraging, the results lack generality for a
629 broader conclusion on the potential of the SUP concept. Whether SUP systems repre-
630 sent an enabling technology for large-scale AU in the context of marine CDR has to
631 be assessed based on a broader set of ocean and geometry data. Further considerations
632 like seasonal performance variations and upscaling of flow rates play a role. The au-
633 thors hope that the present work can provide new insights and methodologies to inform
634 these assessments in the future.

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644 **Appendix A. Full equations for the SPID method**

645 The equations of the *SPID* method were given in Section 2.2 in a generalized form,
 646 as

$$647 \quad c_f \frac{\hat{\rho}}{2} \frac{w^2}{D_h} L = g \left| \int_{z_{top}}^{z_{top}+L} (\rho_{ocean}(z) - \rho(z)) dz \right|, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$648 \quad -A_c w \hat{\rho} c_p(z) \Theta'(z) + C_h U(z) (\Theta_{ot}(z) - \Theta(z)) = 0, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

650 and

$$651 \quad \rho = f(S_A, \Theta, P). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

652 For specific types of SUP systems, the terms take the form given in Table A.3.

	sSUP	satSUP inner pipe	satSUP shell	Equation
D_h	D	D_i	$\frac{D_o^2 - nD_e^2}{D_o + nD_e}$	(A.1)
A_c	$\frac{\pi}{4} D^2$	$n \frac{\pi}{4} D_i^2$	$\frac{\pi}{4} (D_o^2 - nD_e^2)$	(A.2)
C_h	πD	$n\pi D_i$	$n\pi D_e$	(A.2)
Θ_{ot}	Θ_{ocean}	Θ_o	Θ_i	(A.2)
U	$\frac{1}{D \Sigma(D_m/h_m)}$	$\frac{1}{D_i \Sigma(D_m/h_m)}$	$\frac{1}{D_e \Sigma(D_m/h_m)}$	(A.2)
$\Sigma(D_m/h_m)$	$\frac{1}{N_D \kappa} + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{wall}} \ln\left(\frac{D_c}{D}\right) + \frac{1}{N_{De} \kappa_{ocean}}$	$\frac{1}{N_{Di} \kappa_i} + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{wall}} \ln\left(\frac{D_e}{D_i}\right) + \frac{D_{ho}}{D_e N_{Dho} \kappa_o}$	$\frac{1}{N_{De} \kappa_e} + \frac{1}{2\kappa_{wall}} \ln\left(\frac{D_e}{D_i}\right) + \frac{D_{ho}}{D_e N_{Dho} \kappa_o}$	

Table A.3: Definition of the terms in the *SPID* model equations for single SUP (sSUP) systems as well as shell-and-tube type SUP systems (satSUP). Counterflow SUP (cSUP) systems are treated like satSUP systems with a single inner pipe ($n = 1$).

653 For the sSUP system, $D_e = D + 2s$ is the outside diameter of the pipe while N_D
 654 and N_{De} are the diameter-based Nusselt numbers (with respect to D and D_e) of the
 655 convection inside and outside of the pipe wall.

656 Note that cSUP systems are treated as satSUP systems with a single inner pipe in
657 Table A.3. The number of inner pipes is given by n . For cSUP and satSUP systems, D_i
658 and $D_e = D + 2s$ are the inside and outside diameter of the inner pipe, while D_o is the
659 inside diameter of the shell and D_{ho} represents the hydraulic diameter of the shell. The
660 Nusselt numbers for the inner-pipe and shell-side flow are N_{Di} and N_{Dho} , respectively
661 (i. e., with respect to the diameters D_i and D_{ho}).

662 Further, s and κ_{wall} are the thickness and thermal conductivity of the (inner) pipe
663 wall, while κ_i , κ_o and κ_{ocean} are the thermal conductivities of the seawater in the inner
664 pipe, shell, and background ocean, respectively.

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